

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A spatiotemporal comparison of Google search trends between root canal treatment and tooth extraction: A descriptive study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Google trends (GT) is a comparative keyword research website that may be used for the investigation of search trends involving individuals seeking dental health services. This study aimed to compare the search trends between tooth extraction (TE) and root canal treatment (RCT) in the Philippines from 2004-2022. **Methods:** GT was used to compare the keywords “tooth extraction” or TE and “root canal treatment” or RCT. The Philippines was chosen as the country, focusing on sub-region. Timeline of data observed was from the year 2004 to 2022, category is under Health with web search as database. **Results:** The search trends for both keywords peaked in the same year, wherein TE peaked last February 2004 with 96%. In comparison, the search for RCT peaked last May 2004 with a higher percentage of 100%. However, overall search for TE still showed a higher percentage of searches from 2010 to 2022 compared to RCT. **Discussion:** The search for TE shows significantly higher results compared to RCT searches from 2004-2022 in the Philippines. **Conclusions:** When compared to RCT, tooth extraction attracted more attention from Filipinos based on web searches. Despite the fact that RCT searches peaked in popularity in May 2004.

Keywords root canal therapy, tooth extraction, dental health services, spatiotemporal analysis

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1 | Introduction

According to Dziarnowska, et al., searches for “toothache” have

increased which implies that there is a greater impact on the need for dental treatment in the post-pandemic period. There was also a decrease in “dentist” queries during the lockdown period. Google trends can be a means of surveillance for dentists on the needs

of the public with regard to oral health care.¹

Dentistry provides numerous procedures made available for different kinds of situations. Two of the most common dental procedures encountered in the field of dentistry are tooth extraction and root canal treatment. According to Parirokh et al., toothache is prevalent in the community which encourages patients to seek comfort or relief. Tooth extraction (TE) and root canal treatment (RCT), in most cases, are the administered dental procedures.² Another source, Wigsten, E. et al., says that there was a positive impact perceived in the initiation of RCT with regards to health-related quality of life. Overall high satisfaction was registered by involved patients in general dental practice with regards to RCT.³ The branch of endodontics has progressed and developed further over the years which has been a major contribution to the success rates involving root canal treatment. Despite the existence of studies involving RCT and its impact, a large population of people still refuse this treatment and instead proceed with TE. There are instances wherein root canal treatment may be the best option, yet there is still a huge tendency of patients to lean towards TE because of reasons related to having to go through a painful process. Others, and the majority of people, have reasons involving the financial

aspect of endodontic treatment. According to Liszewska et al., the cost of the procedure may tend to be too expensive for some patients.⁴

The lack of ideas on the various dental treatments makes a huge difference on choices and perspectives of individuals. Lack of ideas on a certain matter would mean that there is also lack of patient education which encourages patients to go for the cheaper cost, despite the negative impacts it may bring upon in the future. In dentistry, the main goal is to preserve the natural dentition and its structures as much as possible. According to Bansal et al., awareness towards maintaining a healthy dentition should be given importance as patient education would be a means for patients to consider other dental procedures such as RCT rather than TE.⁵ If there is more awareness regarding various dental treatments, more patients would be encouraged to go for those treatments to preserve teeth, rather than expelling a tooth which could still be saved. Better understanding of different dental treatments would allow understanding on benefits and risks of treatment involving their dentition at present and in the future.⁶

Google Trends (GT) is a website found online that can freely be accessed by the public, especially for those individuals who have an interest in analyzing popular search trends or

Figure 1. Interest over time in the searches for tooth extraction vs. root canal treatment from 2004-2022 in the Philippines.

queries on the internet. This website can serve as a useful tool when wanting to determine the popularity of certain topics. According to Nuti et. al., GT is utilized in numerous ways to examine health phenomena across a wide range of subject areas.⁷ This study compared search trends between TE and RCT in the Philippines and observed the health-seeking behavior of Filipinos with regards to dental services such as TE and RCT. Through this study, dentists would be able to benefit as there would be a greater understanding of the patient’s perspective towards dental treatment.

2 | Results

2.1. Interest over time

The search for both keywords peaked in the same year, wherein tooth extraction (TE) peaked last February 2004 with 96%, while the search for root canal treatment (RCT) peaked last May 2004 with 100%.

The interest of Filipinos in TE and RCT fluctuated from January 2004 to January 2013 with the number of searches listed from 0 as the lowest to

100 searches (May 2004) recorded in RCT. From February 2013, the interest of the Filipinos over time increased a little for TE and remained to have small fluctuations not reaching 0 until August 2022. The highest search for TE was made in February 2004, while the highest search for RCT was in May 2004. Opposite to these results, the search for TE was at its lowest in several months in the years 2004, 2005, and 2006 wherein searches were found at 0% on these certain months of the mentioned years. For RCT, lowest searches were found to be made in certain months in the years 2004-2011. There were months within these years wherein searches went up but only at a minimal percentage. The lowest percentage of searches for these years, in certain months, were also at 0%. Presently, as of August 2022, searches for TE were still higher by 31%, whereas searches for RCT were found at 2%. (Figure 1)

● tooth extraction ● root canal treatment

Figure 2. A compared breakdown by subregion for the searches of tooth extraction vs. root canal treatment from 2004-2022 in the Philippines.

2.2 Compared breakdown by sub-region

In terms of the highest searches for TE, Cordillera Administrative Region (100%) ranked first in subregions followed by Western Visayas (100%), CALABARZON (91%), Ilocos region (100%), Cagayan Valley (100%) and Eastern Visayas (100%). For the interest of RCT, CALABARZON (9%) ranked first followed by Central Visayas (9%), Metro Manila (9%), Central Luzon (8%), Cordillera Administrative Region (0%). (Figure 2)

Looking at figure 2, it shows that at least 8-9% in 4 places namely, Calabarzon, Metro Manila, Central Visayas, and Central Luzon, are noted to be interested in RCT and almost the majority of the places in the Philippines are 100% interested in TE in comparison to RCT. Furthermore, the results indicated that the mean of the people who prefer tooth extraction is 13.19% which is greater than the score of the individuals who preferred RCT

with an average of 2.92% in a span of 18 years from 2004-2022.

3 | Discussion

In this descriptive study, the STROBE (<https://bit.ly/3AK88w5>) reporting guidelines was used to facilitate proper discussion of the results.⁸ Based on the results gathered in GT between TE and RCT from 2004 to 2022 in the Philippines, it shows that TE has more searches as compared to RCT. Searches for tooth extraction gained more interest in 2004 with 100% results. Also, based on the survey results of the regions on whether they are interested in TE or RCT, the results show that 12 out of 16 regions who participated has a percentage of 75% of patients who have presented an interest in TE. On the other hand, the four remaining regions who were not at a 100% still have a higher percentage. These regions are as follows: Calabarzon with 91%, Metro Manila with 91%, Central Visayas with 91%, and Central Luzon with 92%. The aforementioned regions have a commonality as these regions are more urbanized areas in the Philippines which may be the reason for the citizens in these areas to have a greater interest in searching for RCT due to better understanding on this type of treatment. Even though they did not reach 100%, it is still at 90% which shows that TE has been the go-to choice of patients in the country as

compared to RCT, which was shown interest by four regions namely, Calabarzon, Metro Manila, and Central Visayas with 4%, and Central Luzon with 8%. According to Parirokh et al., toothache is prevalent in the community which encourages patients to seek comfort or relief. TE and RCT, in most cases, are the administered dental procedures.² According to the results, people gained more interest with TE than RCT. This may be due to the lack of adequate knowledge among individuals on said treatments. RCT is also a procedure that is feared by the masses.⁵ Studies have reported that anxiety and fear are major factors that hinder individuals from proceeding with RCT.⁴ It may seem that TE is the simpler procedure. However, it may tend to be more complex than it seems. There are higher risks of getting an infection with TE.⁹ This may happen as when the tooth has been extracted, you are left with an empty space that may be a root to the start of build-up of bacteria that can rapidly spread, especially with patients who do not follow proper treatment after-care procedures. There may be patients who, after TE, would automatically neglect the dentist's after-care instructions that would be needed by the patient to prevent any negative side effects while the socket is healing. A missing tooth may also emerge as another complication for neighboring teeth. Opposing teeth do not get any

support and may begin to weaken structures in the mouth, causing overlapping and misalignment. Another occurrence that may happen as well would be drifting of adjacent teeth to the newly vacant space in the mouth. Tooth migration tends to happen months after TE, especially when there is no replacement being made with regard to the involved teeth. Prosthodontics should come in this situation in order to prevent drifting of neighboring teeth, as well as supraeruption of opposing teeth.

RCT can be a painful procedure that will lead to damage to the enamel when not done properly. Keeping the tooth is the best option as this is a manner of conserving the natural dentition. Providing the proper root canal procedure, together with good oral hygiene practice, would enable better healing of the involved tooth and prevent the need for additional treatments or visits. Having the original tooth in place keeps the jaw in line, stays firm and prevents possible tooth migration, and even supraeruption of opposing teeth. Also, there is a better likelihood of lessened visits to the dentist which is something that patients would rather have. TE and RCT both have their pros and cons, but ultimately, the treatment procedure to be administered would depend on the patient's decision. But for the most part, when it comes to tooth conservation, RCT is the better option.³

The results we have gathered and analyzed helps us researchers, as well as licensed dentists, in figuring out the behavior and attitude of Filipinos towards their preference between TE and RCT. The readers can also benefit from this study and get an idea on both procedures by weighing their pros and cons, which would help decide on what procedure will be better for them when they encounter these situations. These results should be considered when considering which treatment to choose between TE and RCT. Statistical data, via the use of google trends (GT), also pledges a great contribution for a clearer understanding on the mass preference, which in this case, is TE. We are able to understand better why there is a larger majority of patients who come into the clinic desiring tooth extraction, rather than asking for other available treatments. The desire to acquire TE could also be due to financial obstacles which patients may be experiencing. Another factor could also be due to lack of patient education with regards to the possible outcomes of such treatment which leads them to choosing the more popular procedure. This study may also give the readers an insight into the differences of treatments and which would be a soothing and advantageous procedure for them. Our expectations with the result have been met, that TE is more likely to be chosen by the patients than RCT as it is more budget friendly and

the most common procedure done, based on the research we have made, as well as the data collected through GT.

4 | Methods

4.1. Data acquisition

Google Trends (GT) website was used to compare the terms “tooth extraction” and “root canal treatment” were used. Google Trends website was accessed on August 15, 2022, at 11:00 in the evening. The Philippines was chosen as the country to be observed with a focus on several of its subregions namely, Metro Manila, Central Luzon, Calabarzon, Western Visayas, Eastern Visayas, Central Visayas, Cordillera Administrative Region, Ilocos Region, and Cagayan Valley. The timeline being observed was from the year 2004 to 2022. The category chosen was under Health and having web search as a database.

4.2. Statistical analysis

A descriptive analysis was being made using the graphic representation of the comparison between tooth extraction vs root canal treatment in GT with the use of a line graph as well as a map graph for the subregions. The results of the searches were shown in percentages.

5 | Conclusions

This descriptive study reveals that TE has more searches as compared to RCT. It is evident that a few of the correspondents are interested in RCT, but the vast majority are more interested in the search for TE. In the Philippines, oral disease is still a

significant public health issue. It does not only cause pain and discomfort to an individual's lifestyle, but it can also ruin a person's smile, appearance, and even one's self-confidence. But, not many Filipinos may consider it as one of their priorities. Factors such as the lack of money, time and awareness can all contribute to failures in visiting a dental clinic. The cost of TE is quite cheap as compared to other dental services being offered in the clinic. Free TE has been rampant around the Philippines given by different medical-dental charity works and organizations. TE may cause several problems like crooked teeth, bone loss and such as time progresses, but with the lack of perception about different dental options in saving a tooth, as well as awareness of the long-term effect of TE, it has always been the go-to treatment for most dental problems in the country.

Between the two options, RCT, among the general population of the country, is undervalued due to the lack of knowledge and the misconceptions of expensive treatment. The cost of having a tooth extracted and replaced with either a fixed or implant-supported restoration would cost as much if not more. There may be risks in proceeding with RCT but if done properly, it can be a long-term investment into the health and aesthetics of the smile. It could also be a better option when considering

functionality of the tooth. Financial factors may play a big role when it comes to choosing dental services, but most of these services, which include RCT, are provided for free among junior and senior clinicians in dental schools with the provision of a licensed clinical instructor.

Moreover, comparing the two dental options TE and RCT, RCT has a better success rate than that of TE. Despite the higher search rate of TE in the Philippines, RCT will not only be a means of saving the natural tooth of the patient, but it also saves the patient's dentition from future complications like malocclusions and such. But then again, due to lack of dental health awareness, extraction became common and practical when choosing a method in treating a diseased tooth among many.

Author Contributions

C.K.Y.: Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Conceptualization; D.F.B.: Writing - Review & Editing, Writing - Original Draft, Validation, Formal Analysis; D.R.N.: Writing - Review & Editing, Writing - Original Draft, Resources, Data Curation; J.M.T.: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing; A.S.: Writing - Review & Editing, Writing - Original Draft, Methodology

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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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